
Innovation of Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in Improving Istima' Skills for Arabic Students in Stain Bengkalis

Triana Susanti¹, Aprijon Efendi², Masrun³, Roinah⁴, Chanifuddin⁵, Marhamah Ulfa⁶, Edi Suyanto⁷, Salahudin Al Asadullah⁸, Sri Rahmadani⁹

^{1,4,5,6,7,8,9} STAIN Bengkalis, Riau, Indonesia

^{2,3} State Islamic University of Sultan Syarif Kasim, Riau, Indonesia

ABSTRACT : Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application is an application that can be used as a learning medium for Istima's proficiency. This development research aims to produce valid and effective Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications. This study uses Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application with material from the book al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha, the book of the beginning, Kitab alif by Dr Abd ar-Rahman Bin Ibrahim al-Fawzan. This research was conducted using the Plomp development model integrated with the Luther development model. The subjects of this study were students of the Arabic Language Study Program in the second semester of STAIN Bengkalis. Two data collection techniques are used in this study, namely, validity obtained through validation by material and media validators and effectiveness in increasing Istima's proficiency from the test. The results showed that the average validity value for the material was 3.8, and the average value was 3.75. The effectiveness of the Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in increasing students' Istima Proficiency based on the results of hypothesis testing (T-Test) in the table above shows that the significance value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05.

KEYWORDS: Research Study, Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application Application, Istima' proficiency

INTRODUCTION

The development of science and technology has brought significant changes to various dimensions of human life, both economic, social, cultural and educational. So that developments in science and technology do not leave education behind, adjustments need to be made, especially those relating to teaching factors in schools.

One of the adjustment factors related to teaching is the learning media teachers need to learn and master to deliver lesson material to students in a good, efficient and effective manner. (H. Asnawir & Usman, 2002)

Hamalik (in Arsyad, 1997) stated that using teaching media in the teaching and learning process can generate new desires and interests, generate motivation, stimulate learning activities, and even psychologically influence students. Using teaching media at the teaching orientation stage will significantly help the effectiveness of the learning process and delivery of lesson content at that time. In addition to arousing student motivation and interest, teaching media can also help students improve understanding, present data excitingly, and make it easier to interpret data and condense information.

Media use in the learning process can arouse students' interest and motivation to learn, reduce or avoid verbalism, generate orderly, systematic reasoning, foster understanding, and develop values in students.

Dale's Cone of Experience is one of the images most often used as a reference and a theoretical basis for using media in teaching and learning. The influence of media on learning can be seen from the level of learning experience that students will receive. A person's learning outcomes are obtained starting from direct (concrete) experience, the reality that exists in a person's life environment, and then through artificial objects and verbal symbols (abstract) (Ali, 2009).

The book al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha kitab awwal, kitab alif by Dr Abd ar-Rahman Bin Ibrahim al-Fawzan. The Al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaik textbook is a type of Arabic language learning book that is still often used in the world of Arabic language education in Indonesia. This book presents many topics about elements of Islamic and Arabic culture with exciting presentations and has very high educational value (Prananingrum & Nurhuda, 2021). This book is equipped with a CD as a learning medium containing audio conversations, mufradat, etc., so it can be used as teaching material for Istima skills. Because text (visual media) and sound (audio media) are separate, researchers innovated to create an application by combining text and sound in al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha kitab awwal, kitab alif. This application is named Praktis (Praktek Istima'). This Android-based application can be downloaded from the Play Store. This application also contains material in sound and written form. This application, equipped with a voice speed-up button of up to 1.5 times, can be accessed offline without an internet data quota.

METHODE

This type of research is Development research; this research was carried out in the even semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. The limited trial in this research was carried out at the STAIN Bengkalis Arabic Language Education Study Program on second-semester students. This research began in April to October 2022. The subjects in this research were students of the second semester Arabic Language Education Study Program class of 2021 with learning media using Praktis (Praktek Istimia') Applications from the book al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha kitab awwal, kitab alif.

The expected result of this research is the use of Praktis (Praktek Istimia') Applications as a learning medium presented validly and effectively and as a learning support for improving students' Istimia' skills..

This research refers to two development models, namely the Plomp (Hobri, 2009) and Luther (Sutopo, 2012) development models. The Plomp model has stages that focus on developing learning products more thoroughly and systematically. The Plomp model consists of 5 stages, namely initial investigation, design, realization/construction, evaluation and revision, and implementation. Luther's development model is oriented towards a product development model. There are several steps in Luther's development, namely, concept, design, material collecting, assembly, testing and distribution.

The data collection instruments used in this research were validation sheets and learning outcomes. The validation sheet is used to measure the validity of the media created by the researcher. The validity of this media was validated by two expert validators. Then, the effectiveness in improving students' Istimia' skills is measured using a learning evaluation test..

1 Data Collection Techniques

a. Media Validity Analysis

The assessment is carried out by an expert validator and one practitioner validator covering aspects, namely format, content, language, simplicity, integration, balance, shape and colour.

Validity criteria according to Khabibah (Yamasari, 2010)

$3 \leq RTV \leq 4 = \text{valid}$

$2 \leq RTV < 3 = \text{cukup valid}$

$1 \leq RTV < 2 = \text{tidak valid}$

The assessment is carried out by an expert validator and one practitioner validator covering aspects, namely format, content, language, simplicity, integration, balance, shape and colour.

The results of this analysis can be used to determine validity because both validators are competent people. Revisions were made to multimedia-based learning media until valid media is obtained.

b. Test

This research is a written test (oral Test) used to test the ability and extent of students' understanding of listening to Arabic texts. The tests carried out are an initial test and a final test at the end of learning.

This initial Test, in the form of a pretest, is carried out on students before being given treatment. This Test is intended to determine the extent of students' mastery of the ability to hear Arabic texts. After it is carried out, a post-test is held to determine the improvement in students' ability to hear Arabic texts (Sudijono, 1997)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research into learning media development using Praktis (Praktek Istimia') applications uses two adapted development models, namely the Plomp development model and the Luther development model. The Plomp development model consists of 5 stages: initial investigation, design, realization/construction, evaluation and revision, and implementation.

Luther's model consists of 6 stages: concept, design, material collecting, assembly, testing, and distribution.

a) Preliminary investigation

1) Preliminary Observation

A preliminary investigation was carried out to collect information regarding the learning difficulties experienced by students as input in designing learning media, which could become a learning resource.

Some of the learning difficulties found were that learning media was only audio and whiteboard. In this case, the use of learning media is limited.

Multimedia is one type of learning media. Multimedia is a combination of media, including animation and video. The use of multimedia is more profitable in some teaching conditions than mono-media (one type of media), such as whiteboards and cassette players. A particular advantage of multimedia is the possibility of using the most appropriate media for the required message, for example, graphics to depict spatial images and animation for moving messages (Philips, 1997).

2) Curriculum Analysis

Curriculum analysis is done by formulating instructional objectives based on essential competencies and indicators listed in the curriculum regarding a material concept, followed by material analysis, where the activities carried out are identifying, detailing, and systematically compiling concepts for the subject matter. Material analysis is carried out to determine the understanding that

Innovation of Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in Improving Istima' Skills For Arabic Students in Stain Bengkalis

students must master to achieve essential competencies and learning objectives. The study of teaching materials is based on al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha kitab awwal, kitab alif by Dr Abd ar-Rahman Bin Ibrahim al-Fawzan.

b) Designing

The activities carried out at this stage are more focused on the results obtained at the initial investigation stage, and then a solution is designed. The following are the stages carried out using Luther's development model:

1) Design

In this stage, the researcher creates a new application that is used to develop multimedia-based learning media, namely Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application. Researchers innovate by combining material in the form of text and sound in one space contained in the application. This application is specifically for Android users. This application can also be accessed online. In addition, this application can be accelerated 1.5 times for listening to sound.

2) Material collecting

The material collecting stage involves collecting the materials needed in the learning media. Making the primary material (subject substance) includes practical applications so that it becomes a learning medium. This application material is taken from the book al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha Kitab Awwal, Kitab Alif by Dr Abd ar-Rahman Bin Ibrahim al-Fawzan.

3) Assembly

The assembly stage is a material script included in each room, and the application is created based on the previous design stages. This stage is carried out by creating a program by the Praktis (Praktek Istima') Applications programmer, which contains concept maps for material from the book al-'Arabiyyah Baina Yadaiki li Ghairi Nathiqina Biha, the book Awwal, the book Alif.

c) Realization/construction

This stage is one of the production stages besides the design stage. In this phase, a media creation technique phase is created, where a development product is produced based on a design that has been designed by integrating media elements, applications and transition techniques into a presentation to become a product. The resulting product is a prime product.

d) Evaluation

This stage considers the quality of the media that has been developed and produced in the form of multimedia-based learning media; then the validator makes ongoing decisions based on the results of the evaluation carried out. Evaluation is the process of collecting, processing and analyzing information systematically to assess learning media that researchers have created. After the evaluation is carried out, a product is produced based on the results of the evaluation carried out by the validator.

Audio and visual design of Praktis (Praktek Istima') Applications and the components contained therein after evaluation and revision, as well as space arrangement in the application.

e) Revision and Validation

1. Revision

Revision activities are carried out after evaluating the products produced. Based on the evaluation results, revisions are carried out by the suggestions given by the validator. After being revised several times, the validator again validated the multimedia-based learning media.

2. Validation

The first validator is a material validator. He is a lecturer at the STAIN Mandailing Natal Arabic Language Education Study Program. The second validator is also a media validator. He is a lecturer at the Arabic Language Education Study Program at UIN Syahada Padang Sidempuan.

The assessment instrument is a validation instrument which consists of two types of instruments.

The first instrument includes validation of material assessed by suitability of the material to learning outcomes, suitability of the material to the student's level, suitability of the material to learning evaluation, suitability of the material to the student's culture, Mufradat in the application is a familiar mufradat.

Validator validation results for media validation can be seen in tabel 1

Table 1. The Result of Validation by the Material Validator

No.	Indicators	Score
1.	Suitability of material to Learning Outcomes	4

Innovation of Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in Improving Istima' Skills For Arabic Students in Stain Bengkalis

2.	Suitability of material to student-level	4
3.	Suitability of material with learning evaluation	4
4.	Suitability of material to student culture	4
5.	The mufradat in the application is the familiar mufradat.	3
Total		19
Average		3.8

Based on the results obtained in the analysis of Table 1, it can be seen that the average validity value for the material is 3.6, which means that the Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in terms of material is included in the "Valid" category based on the criteria mentioned by Khabibah and is on a scale of $3 \leq RTV \leq 4 = \text{valid}$. The average validity value in terms of material validity is 3.8, meaning that this Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application is included in the "Valid" category. It shows that all the components presented in this Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application are suitable for use as material in the teaching and learning process. The second instrument includes media validation regarding interactive learning media design, relevance between the learning media used and teaching materials, ease of use, and availability of learning media used.

Validator validation results for media validation can be seen in the table 2

Table 1. The Result of Validation by the Media Validator

No.	Indicators	Score
1.	Interactive learning media design	3
2.	Relevance between the learning media used and teaching materials	4
3.	Ease in the use of learning media	4
4.	Availability of learning media used	4
Total		15
Average		3.75

Based on the results obtained in the analysis of Table 2, it can be seen that the average validity value for the media is 3.75, which means that the Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in terms of material is included in the "Valid" category based on the criteria mentioned by Khabibah and is on a scale of $3 \leq RTV \leq 4 = \text{valid}$. The average validity value in terms of media validity is 3.75, meaning that this Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application is included in the "Valid" category. It shows that all the components presented in this Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application are suitable for use as media in the teaching and learning process.

f) Try Out

The tryout was carried out to see the extent of the effectiveness and practicality of the media in increasing Istima's skills. Based on the field trials and data analysis results, the trial results began by holding a pretest before learning using Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications and a posttest after learning using Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications.

The following describes the percentage increase in special skills of PBA STAIN Bengkalis students.

Tabel 3. Students' Pretest dan Postest Score

No.	Students' Name	Pretest	Postest
1.	Student 1	65	80
2.	Student 2	65	85
3.	Student 3	70	80
4.	Student 4	70	90
5.	Student 5	60	75
6.	Student 6	60	80
7.	Student 7	60	70
8.	Student 8	75	80

9.	Student 9	65	85
10.	Student 10	70	80
11.	Student 11	65	75
12.	Student 12	60	80
13.	Student 13	70	85
14.	Student 14	75	80
15.	Student 15	65	70
Total		995	1195
Average		66.33	79.66

1. Data Validity and Reliability Test

Validity and reliability tests are used to see the validity and reliability of the instrument using SPSS. If the correlation coefficient is equal to or more than 0.80 then the instrument is declared reliable for measuring the variable.

Based on the results of the validity instrument test, it shows that all instruments are "Valid" with a score of 100%. And based on the results of the reliability instrument test in the table above, it shows that the correlation coefficient is 0.864, which is more than 0.80. It indicates that the test results of the instrument are "Reliable".

2. T-Test

The T-Test using SPSS was used to prove the significant increase in Istima's abilities among Arabic PBA students before using the Praktis (Praktek Istima') application. After using the Praktis (Praktek Istima') application needs to be tested statistically with a correlated (related) t-test.

The results of hypothesis testing (T-Test) in the table above show that the significance value is 0.000, smaller than 0.05. It shows that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. It means there is an increase in the influence of Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications on PBA students' skills.

Final Prototype

The final prototype is the final stage of the entire series of development models, where at the final prototype stage, the resulting product is ready to be used. A learning media product has been produced using Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications at this stage.

Picture 1. Print Screen learning media using Practical Applications.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSION

Based on the presentation of the research results above, it can be concluded that:

1. Praktis (Praktek Istima') application has been validated by 2 experts, namely Learning Media Expert Lecturers and Learning Devices Expert Lecturers. The validation result is "very valid".

Innovation of Praktis (Praktek Istima') Application in Improving Istima' Skills For Arabic Students in Stain Bengkalis

2. Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications can improve students' Istima skills based on the results of hypothesis testing (T-Test). The table above shows that the significance value is 0.000, smaller than 0.05. It shows that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means there is an increase in the influence of Praktis (Praktek Istima') applications on PBA students' skills.

SUGGESTION

Based on the presentation of the research results above, several suggestions are put forward as follows:

3. To develop this Practical Application better.
4. This practical application can be a learning medium for Istima'.
5. Learning using this application can be done anywhere.

REFERENCE

- 1) Ali, M. (2009). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Interaktif Mata Kuliah Medan Elektromagnetik. *Jurnal Edukasi@ Elektro*, 5(1), 11–18.
- 2) H. Asnawir, & Usman, M. B. (2002). *Media Pembelajaran (Cet. I)*. Ciputat Pers.
- 3) Hobri. (2009). *Metodologi Penelitian dan Pengembangan (Developmental Research) (Aplikasi pada Penelitian Pendidikan Matematika)*. FKIP Universitas Jember.
- 4) Philips, R. (1997). *The Developer's Handbook to Interactive Multimedia*. Kogan Page Limited.
- 5) Prananingrum, A. V. P., & Nurhuda, A. N. (2021). Analisis Buku Teks Al-'Arabiyyatu Baina Yadaik Karya Abdurrahman Ibn Ibrahim Al-Fawzan, Dkk. *Proceeding AEC (Arabic Education Conference)*, 1(1), 92–105.
- 6) Sudijono, A. (1997). *Pengantar Statistik Pendidikan*. PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- 7) Sutopo. (2012). *Teknologi dan Informasi dalam Pendidikan*. Graha Ilmu.
- 8) Yamasari, Y. (2010). *Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Matematika Berbasis ICT yang Berkualitas*. FMIPA Unesa.